

CHEMISTRY OF THE RARE-EARTHS. PART III. ESTIMATION OF RARE-EARTHS IN URANIUM MINERALS

BY NIHAR KUMAR DUTT

A critical re-examination of the various methods for the above separation has been made. The method with the help of ether has been improved upon and made suitable for an accurate separation of the rare-earths from excess of uranium.

The problem of the separation of rare-earths and thorium from uranium is of considerable interest for the analysis of uranium minerals like uraninite, pitch blende, etc. In such minerals, the ratio of uranium : rare-earth may be as high as 200. The methods in common use do not afford the clean cut sharpness of separation that is desirable. Though rare-earths can be precipitated quantitatively from acid solution with oxalic acids, the presence of large quantity of uranium has some solvent action on it due to the formation of some complex oxalates. Precipitation of rare-earths in slightly acid solution with ammonium oxalate in presence of salicylic acid, which has been found to form some complex with uranium, has been tried by Canneri and Fernandes (*Gazzetta*, 1924, 55, 770). Hydroxylamine method of Jannasch and Schilling (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1905, 72, ii, 26) gives good results, but the method seems to be tedious since in the filtrate hydroxylamine must be removed before proceeding with the estimation of uranium. The classical reagent for the above separation is hydrofluoric acid used by Lawrence-Smith. Various contradictory results are recorded in the literature for the above separation with the help of ether, the principal reason for this deviation being that dried rare-earths and thorium nitrates have some solubility in anhydrous ether. From a study of the ternary system uranium nitrate—thorium nitrate—ether, it has been shown by Misciattelli (*Phil. Mag.*, 1929, 7, 670) that above 20°, when the ether is saturated with uranium nitrate (which requires 8% of the nitrate), dried thorium nitrate is quite insoluble in it.

A critical review of the various methods for the above separation has been made in the present communication. The method with ether has been developed for the separation of rare-earths from uranium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of standard solutions.—Uranium nitrate, thorium nitrate and rare-earth of 'Kahlbaum' were used. All solutions were standardised by taking an aliquot part and evaporation to dryness and subsequent ignition to oxide. The ether used was purified in the usual manner and dried over metallic sodium.

Oxalic Acid Method.

Thorium can be separated from uranium accurately with oxalic acid even when the ratio U/Th is 200. Rare-earths can only thus be separated when the ratio of U : R.E. is < 25. For higher percentage of uranium the result is always low due to the solvent action as stated above.

TABLE I

Separation of uranium and thorium.

ThO ₂ taken.	Ratio UO ₃ : ThO ₂ .	ThO ₂ found.
0.1244 g.	5	0.1240 g.
0.1244	20	0.1240
0.1244	25	0.1243
0.1244	50	0.1240
0.0622	200	0.0618

TABLE II

Separation of uranium and rare-earth.

Rare-earth taken.	Ratio UO ₃ : R ₂ O ₃ .	R ₂ O ₃ found.	% Error.
0.0543 g.	5	0.0545	—
0.0543	10	0.0543	—
0.0543	25	0.0541	—
0.0543	50	0.0481	7
0.0543	200	0.0426	24

Hydroxylamine Method.

In presence of hydroxylamine, uranium hydroxide is not precipitated by ammonia while rare-earths and thorium are thus precipitated. This method of Jannasch and Schilling (*loc. cit.*) works well up to the limit when uranium is even 100 times that of rare-earths.

TABLE III

Rare-earths taken.	Ratio.	Rare-earths found.
0'1060 g.	10	0'1061 g.
0'0530	50	0'0531
0'0212	75	0'0211
0'0212	100	0'0212

TABLE IV

Rare-earths taken.	Ratio.	Rare-earths found.	% Error.
0'0543 g.	5	0'0543 g.	—
0'0543	10	0'0545	—
0'0543	25	0'0542	—
0'0543	50	0'0522	4
0'0543	100	0'0505	7

Salicylic Acid Method.

This method works well only when the above ratio is lower than 25. With higher percentages of uranium much error is introduced (Table IV).

Hydrofluoric Acid Method.

This method has been used by various workers for the analysis of radio-active minerals. Though this method has been found to work well, it seems to be time-consuming due to the fact that the precipitated fluoride should be decomposed with concentrated sulphuric acid and the anhydrous sulphate should be dissolved in ice water (Table V).

TABLE V

Rare-earths taken.	Ratio.	Rare-earths found.
0'0270 g.	25	0'0271 g.
0'0270	50	0'0270
0'0135	100	0'0135

TABLE VI

Rare-earths taken.	Ratio.	Rare-earths found.
0'0440 g.	100	0'0443 g.
0'0210	200	0'0219
0'0220	400	0'0220

Separation with the help of Ether.

A method based on the use of ether for the separation of rare-earths from uranium has been developed. The principle underlying the method is based on the fact that uranium need not be completely removed before precipitating rare-earths but presence of uranium to the extent of 25 times that of rare-earths does not interfere in the quantitative precipitation of the latter as has been shown by us. And so long as the ether is saturated with uranium nitrate, no rare-earth nitrate goes into solution. Similar observation with thorium nitrate has been made by Misciattelli (*loc. cit.*). Hence by completely drying all the nitrates and also ether and adjusting the volume of ether it has been possible to remove the main bulk of the uranium nitrate present without dissolving any rare-earth nitrate. The residue left is freed from ether, dissolved in water and is then precipitated with oxalic acid as usual, the uranium nitrate left behind with it, does not interfere. This method has been found to work well even when the amount of uranium in the original sample is 400 times that of rare-earths (Table VI.)

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